

is less than that of the other. The latter observation indicates that the higher equilibrium concentration of the ferrocyanide ions which should obtain for the dilute sol does not necessarily mean a greater cataphoretic velocity. At 150 milliequivalents of the ferrocyanide ion, the cataphoretic velocity of the dilute sol is greater. The measurements of cataphoretic speeds for the electrolyte mixtures corresponding to the coagulating systems are also necessary as they may bring out quite different relationships from the above. More extensive measurements are apparently necessary.

The work was carried out in the physical chemistry laboratory, Calcutta University, as a University research scholar from 1930 to 1932 but could not be continued as the writer got an employment.

The author thanks the University of Calcutta for the award of a research scholarship and Prof. J. N. Mukherjee for his advice and facilities for this work.

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Received June 26, 1935.

Preparation of Resorcinol Monomethyl Ether (A Correction).

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My attention has been drawn to certain inaccuracies of a grave character in the details of the method of preparing this substance which appeared in this Journal (1934, 11, 743; 1935, 12, 141). Resorcinol monomethyl ether is practically non-volatile in steam. The correct method is described below.

A solution of pure resorcinol (11 g.) in 10 % caustic soda (40 c.c.) was warmed to 60°-70° and treated with good shaking with pure acid-free dimethyl sulphate (12-13 g.) added in small quantities at a time. The mixture was finally heated on the boiling water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. It was extracted, on cooling, with ether (30 c.c., 25 c.c. and 20 c.c.), the ethereal solution extracted with 10%

caustic soda (30 c. c., 20 c. c.), the alkaline solution acidified in the cold (ice) with HCl (1:1) and the whole then extracted thrice with ether (50, 25 and 20 c. c.). The ethereal solution was dried over calcium chloride, the ether removed on the water-bath and the residue distilled from a small flask (50 c. c.). The fraction passing between 240° — 248° was collected. The amount of the ether, a pale yellow thick oil, obtained in two different experiments, weighed 7.3 g. and 7.4 g. respectively.

The results obtained on carrying out the operation according to the wrong instructions given might also prove to be of interest: On distilling in steam for 2 hours a pale yellow oil (about 2 c. c.) passed over; on treating the distillate in the manner described, 1.5 c. c. of a colourless oil, b. p. 210° . 212° , was isolated and identified with resorcinol dimethyl ether, while hardly a drop of a dark coloured oil soluble in alkali, which might be the monomethyl ether, was obtained. The residual liquid in the steam distillation flask was made alkaline and extracted with ether which removed only a trace of the dimethyl ether. The solution was then acidified and the monomethyl ether which separated as a dark oil was extracted with ether, dried and distilled, yield 6 g. of product (b. p. 240° - 250°).

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Received April 24, 1935.

As the work had been carried out some four years ago I had to consult the old files containing records of work carried out by students in my laboratory. I find that the wrong method had been copied for a thesis by one of my students without regard to a marginal note in my own handwriting in which the correct method had been described. Messrs V. Mahadevan and G. Srinivasan have now carefully repeated the preparation by the correct method under my supervision.
